

STUDYING THE EFFECTS OF SOUND FREQUENCY OF 432 HZ ON HUMANS USING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE (AI)

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Abstract

The 432 Hz indicates that vibration occurs 432 times within a single minute. The effects of frequency of 432 Hz on humans is studied here through the effects it has on EMG signals in an artificial intelligence based studies similar to the one I also conducted on frequency of 440 Hz (Ozuomba U. D., 2025) that many theorists had refused to acknowledge as a tuning standard for musical instruments over frequency of 432 Hz which they deemed to have better health benefits. Moreover, this study helps to divulge if frequency of 432 Hz changes electrical activities of human muscle just as many Igbo acoustic sound instrument such as *ụbọ*, *ọja*, *ọkwa*, *nkelebe*, *ọdụ*, *aro*, *atañiri*, *ekwe*, *igba*, *oyo*, *ogele*, and vocal *elele*. Any changes in electrical activities of human muscle as a consequence of sound waves effects from any of these sound sources can mean detrimental health effects if they are bad, but if good, can mean healthy effects on stress, anxiety, depression, emotion, mood, affect, cognition, pain, immune system, socio-cultural integrations, profitable cooperation, personal growth and improvement as well as general well-being. Meditative sound healing practices involving some of these acoustic sound instruments are employed natively to aid pacification and mitigation of detrimental energies that survive on one's detrimental actions and inactions that in turn drain and impedes their energy, vibrations, frequencies and general growth. These detrimental energies are seemingly karmic, and are termed *akaraogheri*, *uke* and *ogbonuke* in Igbo lingo. The sound frequency of 432 Hz at 30, 60 and 90 decibels were used for this study, and upon healthy exposure poses no health risks. As in others, outcomes may vary in diverse locations due to unwanted and unavoidable sound inputs.

Keywords: Frequency 432 Hz, EMG Signals, Frequency Medicine, CleveLab system, MATLAB, Machine Learning, Sound healing, Sound Therapy, Sound Bath, Energy Healing, Energy Medicine.

INTRODUCTION

Several sound frequencies of different amplitudes had significant effects on electrical activities of humans in several artificial intelligence based-electromyography studies, and the muscle being a fundamental part of the human body can influence human health status via the sound-influenced muscle, thus, the possible therapeutic effects of sound waves with the inclusion of frequency of 432 (Ozuomba U. D., 2025; Ozuomba & Z, 2025; Ozuomba U. D., 2025; Ozuomba U. D., 2025). Frequency of 432 Hz has been shown in a research to have more healing values than 440 Hz where people exposed to it found it more satisfying, focus-inducing and slightly reduced their mean systolic blood pressure, diastolic blood pressure, mean heart rate as well as respiratory rates (Calamassi & Pomponi, 2019). Frequency of 432 Hz is also considered to be in harmony with human body, reducing anxiety and stress, helping the brain to attend high level of relaxation by virtue of its balancing and calming effects, and these wonderful healing virtues have made frequency of 432 Hz a better sound frequency for meditations geared towards achieving both physical and mental healings (ByImmersive Sound Experience , 2024). Sound therapy is a confirmed ancient medical approach (Goldsby & Goldsby, 2020) for healing purposes among other things (Habibi & Damasio, 2014). It is equally termed a holistic healing approach or sound baths that makes use of vibration to actualize healing objectives (Goldsby, Goldsby, McWalters, & Mills, 2016; EliteCare Health Centers, 2023). To the Igbos, sound waves from music have natural qualities to improve people's mental and physical health as well as their spiritual status (Nwobu, 2018). Sound therapy is also

seen as a suitable healing approach to medically combat emergence of diseases among people, and it equally serves as a treatment option for people already affected by disease (Oghenetega , et al., 2022). Sound waves are obviously energy (Raghu , 2018; Choi, Jung, & Kang, 2019) that have health implications if transmitted into the body (Bass & Clark, 2003; World Health Organization, 2018; Reybrouck , Podlipniak, & Welch, 2019).

AIM: The purpose of this study is create an artificial intelligence-based model for prediction and detection of human muscles' response to sound frequency of 432 Hz at amplitudes of 30, 60 and 90 decibels.

MATERIALS USED

1. Frequency generator app with an inbuilt amplitude meter for frequency 432 Hz generation at amplitudes of 30, 60 and 90 decibels.
2. CleveLab kit with five snap electrodes for EMG data collections during the electromyography studies.
3. MATLAB for creation of the artificial intelligence model (AI Model).
4. Healthy Volunteers who took part in the electrography studies.
5. Healthcare staff who monitored the process.

PROCEDURE

Attach electrodes to bicep and wrist extensor muscles of the participating volunteers just as electrodes are attached to their elbow bones to record the effects of frequency of 432 Hz on their EMG signals. Sound frequency of 432 Hz was generated from the sound frequency generator app and applied on the healthy volunteers who participated in the electromyography studies in my laboratory room.

Using CleveLab system, I conducted and recorded each electromyography process for five seconds duration to obtain both graphical and numerical data. However, it is only the numerical data that I used to build the machine learning model in MATLAB software after cleaning and analyzing it in Microsoft Excel. I trained the model using different statistical methods after a careful preprocessing of the data. I employed classification method using MATALAB Tools - Classification Learner precisely. Also made available to detect distinction within the data was a healthcare professional

RESULTS

I obtained both graphical and numerical data from each subject after application of the generated

frequency of 432 Hz at amplitudes of 30, 60 and 90 decibels. Some data information were very minute that even the healthcare professional could not detect them. With a cleaned, analyzed, preprocessed numerical data, I built the AI model and trained it with different statistical methods in MATLAB software. The various models I built using MATLAB software demonstrated differing levels of accuracy, with the highest performance recorded at 75% accuracy with the Ensemble Bagged Tree. [and Ensemble Subspace KNN]. Furthermore, the subjects' muscle response to the 432 Hz signal exhibited a true positive rate (TPR) of 100% at 60 decibels, while the false negative rate (FNR) was 100% at both 30 and 90 decibels.

Figure 1. True positive Rate and False positive Rate.

Figure 1. True Positive Rate and False Negative Rate

CONCLUSION

The AI eventually detected the hidden data information that were not detectable at the initial state. As I have in separate studies on the effects of sound frequency of 440 Hz and that of basal sound waves on humans, the AUC value of this studies involving only sound frequency of 432 Hz at different amplitudes is also 50% despite having an impressive higher accuracy of 75% and highest

response rates of 100%. However, when this same sound frequency of 432 Hz was studied jointly with other sound frequencies across different amplitudes in an EMG and AI-based studies, not only were the model's accuracy and muscle's response rates still high, the AUC value was equally high, indicating obvious sound waves effects on human muscle, good model performance and clinical usefulness (Ozuomba & Z, 2025). In other words, sound

frequency of 432 Hz influences EMG signals, signifying obvious influences on electrical activities of human muscle which can in turn influence human health owing to the fact that muscle tissue is a vital component of virtually all human organs and systems structurally and functionally responsible for human health. So, taking all these facts and findings into consideration, it is a commendable initiative to conduct further research into the health effects of sound frequency of 432 Hz at varying amplitudes, and if possible research into health effects of other sound frequencies across different amplitudes.

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